

Making open innovation work for Sustainable Development Goals: Sustainability-orientation and assessment based on the SDG-Check

Justus von Geibler¹, Julius Piwowar*¹, Annika Greven¹

*Corresponding author

¹ Wuppertal Institute for Climate Environment and Energy, Germany

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Abstract

Accounting for sustainability in early innovation processes proves to be a challenge for corporate practitioners and innovators, largely due to the concept's intangible and qualitative nature as well as a lack of data in early innovation phases. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) published in 2015 by the United Nations provide a globally accepted framework for sustainability and an opportunity to support sustainability assessments in early innovation phases. However, handling the 17 goals and large number of sub goals are a main barrier for innovation practitioners. This paper discusses an online tool called "SDG-Check", which enables sustainability orientation and assessment in early phases of product and service development. It is a semi-quantitative tool to gather and combine assessments of experts involved in the innovation process. The tools built on an online checklist and a stepwise approach which considers two different levels of detail: one level at the 17 goals and another level at the sub goals. The digitalised processing of data enables to assess the large number of data entries and to aggregate and compare the experts' views on the risk and opportunities of the innovation with regard to the SDGs. The first user experiences from applying the SDG Check in three innovation cases highlighted that the tools can support a dialogue with internal and external stakeholders and the improved consideration of sustainability in the early design stages of product and service development.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development Goals; SDG-Check; open innovation; living lab; sustainability assessments*

1 Introduction

In the light of human's impact reaching planetary boundaries (Rockström et al. 2009, Steffen et al. 2015) and various political sustainability objectives, such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the various stakeholders call for an accelerated transition toward sustainability (e.g. Jacob et al. 2016, Jha et al. 2016). Research and innovation are crucial to address this challenge and change production and consumption systems. Especially in early phases of the innovation process there is a specific opportunity for adaptation and changes in the product and service design. Identifying and integrating relevant sustainability aspects as early as possible is therefore important, since product and service design at this stage are still adaptable and early-stage modifications are comparably low-cost to later modifications (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dilemma of Product Innovation (left) and opportunities based on prototyping (right) (Source: own illustration, based on Ullman, 1997)

In order to exploit the sustainability potentials in innovation processes, it is necessary to define appropriate requirements that guide the innovation process and thus minimize or eliminate risks for sustainable development. Especially with an increasing radicalness of an innovation, there is the risk that the embeddedness of an innovation in individual, social or cultural contexts of use is not ensured (Clausen et al. 2011). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) formulated by the United Nations in 2015 (UN, 2015) are universally relevant goals for sustainable development and could be the basis for the requirements that sustainable innovations face in order to achieve these ambitious goals.

Against this background this paper presents a tool for the sustainability orientation and assessment in early stages of innovation based on the SDGs. The concrete tool – the SDG-Check, aiming at identifying and integrating relevant sustainability aspects in early stages of innovation processes, has been proposed by Echternacht et al. 2016. The main objective of the paper is to discuss the SDG-Check as a tool for sustainability orientation and assessment based on the SDGs and in early phases of product and service development. The related research questions are:

- What are the experiences of the SDG-Check in living lab innovation projects?
- How does the SDG-Check enables sustainability assessments in innovation projects with regard to the Sustainability Development Goals?

Structure of the paper

The background on sustainability assessment within open innovation processes is described in section 2 along with the research methodology. The SDG-Check, is described in section 3. Furthermore, the results and experiences from applying the SDG-Check as an online survey tool will be presented and discussed in light of the need for robust and practical sustainability assessments in transformative research and innovation processes. The paper ends with a conclusion (Chapter 4).

2 Approach and methodology

Sustainability assessment in open innovation

In the recent years businesses tend to open their innovation processes and engage societal actors (Howaldt & Schwarz 2012). Stakeholders, other businesses (external partners), as well as consumers, are increasingly included in the development of products and services, even at an early stage of innovation. The concept of open innovation refers to the utilization of in- and outflowing knowledge across company boundaries to accelerate internal innovation (Chesbrough 2003). Open innovation is especially relevant in developing product-service systems along with users and stakeholders (Liedtke *et al.*, 2015). Results show that these concepts can significantly reduce the risk of innovations failing on the market, especially radical innovations in a difficult market or which face technological uncertainties (Clausen et al. 2011, 35).

Involving stakeholder groups definitely requires interactive methods in interdisciplinary processes. Research on ‘co-creation’ and a series of new business models and management tools, which include users in the innovation process, have lately been promoted by concepts of interactive innovation development, such as ‘open innovation’ (Chesbrough 2003), ‘wisdom of crowds’ (Surowiecki 2004) or the ‘lead user’ concept (von Hippel 1986), as well as ‘transformation and transition design’ (Schmidt-Bleek & Tischner 1995; Irwin 2015; Sommer & Welzer 2014). Several interactive methods were developed with stakeholders and users, e.g. to involve non-users and lead users in innovation workshops for sustainable-living innovations (Diehl 2011), or web 2.0 tools to use collective intelligence (Leimeister 2010). Based on the Agile Manifesto (a method to develop software in small steps, with little planning and strong user integration), Cooper 2014 proposes to strengthen user integration.

The integration of user and stakeholder’s perspective also offers the opportunity to integrate sustainability aspects, especially if a wide range of different stakeholder perspectives are

considered. However, the integration of stakeholders also has limitations with regard to the consideration of sustainability. The users might have a limited perspective, rooted in their experience of daily routines, which do not promote radical or disruptive innovation. Also, intense interactions with many stakeholders are time and resource-intensive, which is hindering the innovation process.

The innovation process can be structured in different iterative phases, ranging from three phases, to four, five and even nine phases (Geibler *et al.* 2016). The commonly used stage-gate process with four phases has been chosen as the conceptual frame of the SDG-Check based on the evaluation of the experiences and discussions with relevant stakeholders: context analysis involving preliminary investigation (1) and detailed preliminary investigation (2); prototype development (3); and field test (4) (Liedtke *et al.* 2015). In case of an “ideal” procedure the process can be structured and sectioned by five different points of decision-making (so-called “gates”) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Phases and gates in innovation processes
(Source: translated from Geibler *et al.* 2016)

Assessing the sustainability within open innovation processes requires defining and describing both the innovation and the reference system. Describing the innovation system allows identifying and evaluating the innovation’s sustainability in terms of its techno-physical, usage and cultural causal chain (Paech 2005). The techno-physical causal chain describes the direct effect of the innovation’s production or development, including direct effects upstream. The usage causal chain describes the direct and indirect effect of the innovation’s use or application (rebound effects and upstream) (Buhl *et al.* 2017). The cultural causal chain describes the innovations’ cultural effect. Innovations, which are highly culturally effective, have more impact potential (cultural-institutional transition) than innovations, which only have technical (technical transition) or use-specific effects (systemic transition).

Further, comparing innovation and reference allows estimations of the potential for change

towards sustainability (see Figure 3). If the innovation is already positioned on the market, sustainability and change “effects” can be assessed and analysed (Hansen et al. 2009).

Figure 3. Sustainability impact and potential of an innovation.

Source: Hansen et al. 2009, 686.

Assessing sustainability within innovation processes, stakeholders’ needs and objectives must be defined. Both actively (e.g. employees, users) and passively involved (or “affected”) stakeholders’ groups (e.g. administrative stakeholders) as well as demands, which depend on the objective of the followed development concept (e.g. SDGs), can be included in the innovation process. At the same time there is a need to have a guiding vision and objectives for the analysis (IISD 1997). Gibler *et al.* (2016) suggest an SDG-Check for the assessment of sustainability potentials within the innovation process, referring to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs are broadly defined and reach from fighting poverty to improving education and health to mitigating climate change as well as protecting the oceans and ecosystems. Under the title “Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” the states created a catalogue of 17 goals and 169 subordinate goals; the realization until 2030 is voluntary, but for the first time universally valid, equally for developing, emerging and industrialized countries (IASS Potsdam 2016).

The SDGs can be a point of reference for the sustainability assessment within the innovation process if the SDGs’ topics are checked at the micro level to evaluate an innovation’s sustainability during the innovation process (Geibler *et al.* 2016).

Research methodology

The research process involved three main phases:

Phase 1: Description of the “SDG Check”

The SDG-Check was initiated in a living lab research project (www.innolab-livinglabs.de/en.html; Echternacht et al. 2016) and based on a literature review focusing on conceptual and methodological understanding on sustainability assessments within open innovation processes. In section 3 the development of the SDG-Check is described, focussing on the functional requirements and the concrete steps.

Phase 2: Application of the SDG-Check in three cases

The SDG-Check was applied in three innovation projects within three German Living Labs and involved SMEs as well as research institutes (2016-2017). The innovation objective was to co-create and test a (digital) assistance system, which encourages sustainable consumption in the fields of mobility, living and retail. In total, the SDG-Check was applied in multidisciplinary teams (in total 15 participants) and in two different innovation phases (concept and prototype phase) (see Meurer et al. 2017; Krein et al. 2017; Kahl et al. 2017). In section 3 the results of the SDG-Check are presented.

Phase 3: Evaluation of the SDG-Check application

After application and together with the three innovation project leaders the effectiveness and efficiency of the “SDG-Check” was evaluated. This is based on a survey and discussions in a workshop. The evaluation criteria for the survey are summarized in table 1 and involved a five-scale ranking: (--) very insufficient, (-) insufficient, (0) neutral, (+) good, (++) very good; (n.a.) not applicable (no or insufficient data available).

Table 1: Evaluation criteria for the application of the SDG-Check
(Source: Geibler *et al.* 2018 forthcoming)

Effectiveness	Efficiency
user integration	cost efficiency
user context integration	technical efficiency
social aspects	time efficiency
ecological aspects	usability

3 The SDG Check and Results

Description of the SDG-Check

The SDG-Check focuses on potential effects an innovation could have with regard to the 17 goals and their sub goals. The SDG-Check is designed to raise consciousness for these goals and their thematic diversity, so that the stakeholders are more attentive to options to integrate these goals e.g. in business models. The tool development (Echternacht et al. 2016) was framed by the following requirements:

The *tools objective* is to assess potential sustainability effects (risks and/or opportunities) of an innovation within (early stage) development processes. Furthermore, the tool should enable orientation and a common understanding on sustainability goals and to inspire ideation processes as well as business models. This means, the tool will not be able to measure specific sustainability aspects e.g. on CO₂ emissions.

The *target group* of the tool are members of multidisciplinary innovation teams e.g. engineers, designers, sustainability and non-sustainability experts. The results of the tool are based on individuals and/or groups self-assessment.

The *usability criteria* for the tool are the following: Results of an assessment should be transparent and comparable, e.g. with assessments of users or with later assessments; the application should be intuitive and understandable; sustainability knowledge should not be required; the time needed for the individual tool application should be below 20 minutes.

As a result, the SDG check tool built on a checklist and a stepwise approach with two levels of detail focusing on the 17 SDGs (level 1) and their sub goals (level 2). The goals are evaluated based on a 7-step scale ranging from -3 (severe risk) to +3 (high opportunity).

Step 1 (level 1) of the SDG-Check serves to estimate whether the innovation creates opportunities or risks concerning the 17 UN SDGs. To do this, it is estimated whether the innovations have positive or negative potential with regard to the 17 SDGs using a 7-step scale. The SDG-Check's first step is shown exemplarily in Figure 4.

INNOLAB SDG-Check Step 1

Please estimate whether your innovation idea creates opportunities or risks concerning the 17 SDGs. The innovation should be able to create a positive contribution to at least 3 goals.

risk neutral opportunity
-3 -2 -1 0 1 2 3

1 NO POVERTY Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts		
2 ZERO HUNGER Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development		
3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss		
4 QUALITY EDUCATION Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels		
5 GENDER EQUALITY Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development		
6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns		

Figure 4. SDG-Check STEP 1. Source: Anonymous et al. (2016), Specification of the SDGs based on UN (2015).

Step 2 (level 2) of the SDG-Check can be applied subsequently during the innovation process. Here, the focus is on a selection from the 17 SDGs and their sub goals. The selection covers six main goals of Step 1, which were evaluated with the greatest opportunities (3 goals) and risks (3 goals). The participants evaluate the sub goals in terms of opportunities and risks also using the 7-step scale (ranging from -3 to +3). For the aggregation of the single assessments at goal level the Chance-Risk-Value (CR-Value) is used as a mean of the single assessment values at sub-goal level. As an example, 0 illustrates Step 2 with sub goal questions of the SDG 12 (Responsible consumption and production). The questions for the other sub goals can be found in Echternacht et al. 2016.

INNOLAB SDG-Check Step 2

Please estimate whether your innovation idea creates opportunities or risks concerning the sub goals of the SDG 12.

	The innovation is
	a risk neutral an opportunity
	-3 -2 -1 0 1 2 3
The innovation contributes to sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources .	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation contributes to reduce food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation contributes to environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation contributes to substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation organization intends to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation or the organization promotes public procurement practices that are sustainable , in accordance with national policies and priorities.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation contributes to ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation or the organization contributes to support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■
The innovation contributes to develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable development impacts for sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products.	■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ ■

Figure 5. SDG-Check STEP 2, taking the example of the SDG 12 „Sustainable Production and Consumption“. Source: Based on Geibler *et al.* (2016), Specification of the SDGs based on UN (2015).

Results of the SDG-Check

The SDG-Check results were assessed in three innovation a project and for both Steps 1 and 2. The results are based on the assessments of the participants and calculated as CR-values as well as value range. This enabled to illustrate an SDG ranking, which was presented to the participants for further discussions. As an example, Figure 6 and 7 illustrate results of the SDG-Check. The results are from the innovation project “Retail” involving seven participants.

Figure 6. Results of the SDG Check (Step 1) in the innovation project “Retail” (Source: Kahl et al. 2017, own translation)

Figure 7. Results of the SDG Check (Step 2) in the innovation project “Retail” (Source: Kahl et al. 2017, own translation)

The results show, that the most significant opportunities of the evaluated shopping assistance system are linked to the goals responsible production in consumption, life below water, industry and innovation and infrastructure as well as good health and well-being. In Step 2 it was analysed, that the innovation can contribute to the sub goals of an efficient usage of natural resources, embedding information of sustainability, the protection of sea and coast ecosystems and a reduction of waste (Kahl et al. 2017). Two sub goals have been identified as minor risks that the innovation could affect negatively: Increasing the wealth of the poorest 40% of the population and raising exports to developing countries.

Results on the application of the SDG-Check

The survey and the workshop discussions highlighted that the SDG-Check and its application has been positively evaluated in all three innovation cases. The broad sustainable development goals were directing innovation towards sustainability, without being too restrictive. The reference to the SDGs built confidence and trust within the innovation process, as the SDGs have a very broad consensus and high legitimacy.

The table below summarizes the results of the survey for SDG-Check’s effectiveness and efficiency answered by the project leaders. The results show that the SDG-Check is seen as a cost-efficient tool, which is easy and quick to use and promotes ecological benefits. The SDG-Check is not very time consuming (>30 minutes) and is intuitively based on a simple and standard evaluation scheme (with a scale between 1 and 7).

Table 2. Overview of the method assessment based on the survey results (Source: Geibler *et al.* 2018 forthcoming)

Effectiveness	Score*	Efficiency	Score*
User integration	0	Cost efficiency	++
User context integration	+	Technical efficiency	+
Social aspects	0	Time efficiency	+
Ecological aspects	++	Usability	++

*Legend: (--) very insufficient, (-) insufficient, (0) neutral, (+) good, (++) very good; the assessment is based on the mean value.

The following experiences have been made in the innovation project “retail” (Kahl et al. 2017):

- Based on the SDG-Check first quantitative evaluation results could be documented, which complement qualitative assessments.
- The SDG-Check is not very time consuming (shorter than 30 minutes) and is intuitively based on a simple and standard evaluation scheme (with a scale between 1 and 7).
- A harmonised communication within the project team about sustainability has been enabled by the SDG-Check. The Check has been a platform for the development of a common understanding of sustainability and sustainability goals. However, without an introduction and explanation the SDGs can be abstract and unstructured and reduce the motivation to deal more closely with the SDG theme / sustainability and to take appropriate measures for product design into consideration.
- The complexity of the Goals covering 17 goals and 169 targets can lead to mental *overload* and demotivation. However, the SDGs' communicative potential is very high because of their international recognition. They can be combined with other company-relevant methods (such as the SDG Compass) and can serve as the basis for an enterprise-internal sustainability strategy (CSR).
- The SDG-Check can also inspire new business models.
- An in-depth analysis (such as a hotspot analysis) could not be performed within the framework of the project. For an effective sustainability analysis this would be sensible: the selection of the goal and targets does not necessarily have to be the most significant sustainability potentials of innovation. The selection is based on a self-assessment, which can be used as a basis for the further dialogue and should be evaluated by other experts.

4 Conclusion

The assessment of the early product and service design phases is of major importance since these early stages influence a high share of the cost spent for a product (i.e. production costs, maintenance costs and end-of-life costs). Similarly, the environmental and social potential of an innovation are also determined in early stages of process development.

Considering the complexity of technological implication on sustainability, it is necessary to assist innovators in developing and implementing technological innovations and the consideration of sustainability. New tools and capabilities in organisations are needed to make use of technological opportunities and to reduce their economic, environmental and social risks. The presented SDG Check is being developed to support the assessment of social aspect in early stages of biotechnological process development.

However, the single application of the assessment tool alone will not be sufficient to support sustainable innovations. Along with evaluations it is necessary to develop a responsibly minded innovation culture. A corporate culture that promotes the “ability to learn” - the central point of our ability to innovate more sustainable production and consumption patterns. Future research should be conducted based on a broader application of the SDG-Check in other cases. Hereby the SDG-Check should be compared with other approaches focusing on innovation development at an early stage e.g. Biomimicry 3.8 (Baumeister et al. 2013); the 10 Golden Rules (Luttropp n.d.) or the AttrakDiff 2 (UID 2018).

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